

High Power Integrated DFB-EAM-SOA for beyond 35 dB Optical Path Loss 50G-PON and Raman Scattering Estimations

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Abstract We evaluate the performances of a TOSA-packaged integrated DFB-EAM-SOA achieving +13.3 dBm mean launch power at 50 Gb/s. Up to 38.5 dB optical path losses are achieved, exceeding the class D requirements for future deployment. We discuss the non-linear effects triggered by such high-power levels. ©2023 The Author(s)

Introduction

Passive Optical Networks (PONs) are the reference for broadband optical access. ITU-T's Gigabit-capable PON (G-PON) is today widely deployed, and 10-Gigabit-capable symmetric PON (XGS-PON) mass deployment started [1]. The ITU-T is currently working on XGS-PON successors, the 50-Gigabit-capable PON (50G-PON) with a line rate of 50 Gb/s, and the Very High Speed PON showing a line rate of at least 100 Gb/s in downstream.

Regarding 50G-PON, while the main specifications were released some years ago [2], debates still animate the community on the way to meet the high Optical Path Loss (OPL) requirements. While B+ class (13-28 dB, [3]) and 1:64 splitting ratio were the reference in the first stages of G-PON deployment, some operators already reconfigure their Optical Distribution Networks (ODNs) to 1:128 splitting ratio in combining two legacy ODNs. One of the reasons for this evolution is driven by the carbon footprint reduction objectives [4], [5], as less Optical Line Terminal (OLT) cards and ports will be used. As a result, 50G-PON technologies specifications include high OPL with classes C+ (17-32 dB) and even E2 [2] (20-35 dB, referred as class D in [3] when no Multiple PON module is used).

Recent works showed that the receivers considered viable for downstream 50G-PON were reaching the sensitivity limits [6], [7], [8], [9] despite of the high performance Forward Error

Correction (FEC) selected for 50G-PON. To meet high OPL class requirement, the solution is to increase the launched power at OLT side. While class D specifications are for further study, B+ and C+ specifications already consider a mean launched power in the range of 4.5-10 dBm and 8.5-14 dBm, respectively [3]. This pushes the barriers of emitters conception beyond limits in terms of both launched power and electro-optical bandwidth, considering the line rate and the need for higher OPL class (class D).

Several works addressed this issue: in [10], the authors reported a Distributed Feedback (DFB) Electro Absorption Modulated (EAM) emitter delivering 13.0 dBm output facet average modulated power. Similarly, in [11], the authors demonstrate 15.3 dBm dynamic output power with integrating sphere with a Chip-on-Carrier (CoC) using a DFB-EAM integrated with a Semiconductor Optical Amplifier (SOA). In [12], the authors showed a performance of 10.9 dBm EML-SOA integrated in TO-Can package.

Here, we demonstrate the performances of a DFB-EAM-SOA, embedded in a Transmitter Optical Subassembly (TOSA) exhibiting up to 13.3 dBm dynamic output power and 15.9 dBm static power. The TOSA integration represents a major step compared to CoC, as it considers the non-negligible insertion losses inherent to coupling. The characteristics of the DFB-EAM-SOA TOSA are presented. Real time transmissions performances at 50 Gb/s are also

Fig. 1: a) Schematic structure of the chip. b) The TOSA. c) Output power and DFB bias depending on the DFB bias current (SOA bias: 100mA). d) TOSA's spectrum (SOA is in operation. A 5 dB attenuation was used to preserve the OSA).

measured, demonstrating up to 38.5 dB OPLs, exceeding the class D requirements. The penalty due to stimulated Raman scattering are also estimated for the future class D specifications.

Device Structure and Static Characterization

Fig. 1.a shows the schematic drawing of the DFB-EAM-SOA chip device. A typical electro-absorption-modulated laser (EML) device structure designed to operate at 50 GBaud rate is used for the DFB-EAM section, which consists of a buried DFB laser diode integrated with an EAM by butt-coupling. The SOA integrated in front of the EAM enables the transmitter to achieve the high optical power required by ITU-T 50G-PON OLT, without compromising the EML's large extinction ratio and broad bandwidth. The structure of the SOA is optimized to suppress gain saturation which can cause transmitter waveform distortion and to achieve the high output power simultaneously.

Fig. 1.b shows the TOSA, and Fig. 1.c its output power and voltage as a function of the DFB current, while the EAM bias is set to 0 V and the SOA bias to 100 mA. An output power of 38.8 mW (15.9 dBm) is achieved when the DFB section is biased at 140 mA and the Thermo-Electrical Cooler (TEC) targets room temperature (24 °C). The spectrum of Fig. 1.d shows a Side Mode Suppression Ratio (SMSR) of 54 dB and a peak wavelength at 1340.4 nm. This value is in the specified wavelength range (1340-1344 nm) for downstream 50G-PON [2]. The Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE) floor of the SOA is 60 dB below the peak, thus optimizing the output power.

Fig. 2: Dependence of the transient chirp parameter (“alpha”) with the EAM bias, and frequency domain optical channel for EAM bias of -1.4 V (insight)

Chromatic Dispersion (CD) is one of the main sources of Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) in the optical path. Its association with transient chirp (quantified by the so-called “alpha parameter”) originating from EAM modulation exacerbates the phenomenon [8] at the considered bitrate. The chirp dependence on the EAM bias was measured using the method introduced in [13], consisting in a frequency domain optical path

estimation and a model fitting. The transient chirp under operating condition (EAM bias around -1.4 V) was $\alpha=0.3$, as shows Fig. 2.

The electro-optical bandwidth of the components is the other source of ISI. Fig. 3 shows the transfer function of the TOSA, displaying a -3 dB bandwidth of 31 GHz.

Fig. 3: Transfer function of the TOSA

Transmission Experimental Setup

Fig. 4 represents the experimental setup. The DFB section is biased at 120 mA. The SOA current is set to 100 mA and the TEC sets the TOSA to room temperature. A bias tee mixes the EAM bias of -1.4V with a $2^{31}-1$ bits long Pseudo Random Binary Sequence (PRBS) electrical signal modulated at 2.9 Vpp amplitude (twice the EAM bias) in Non-Return-to-Zero (NRZ) modulation format. The bitrate is set to 50 Gb/s which corresponds to the 50G-PON downstream line rate.

Fig. 4: Experimental setup

The optical transmission channel consists in a variable length of standard Single Mode Fibre (SMF) and a Variable Optical attenuator (VOA). The receiver consists in an integrated 25G-class Avalanche Photodiode (APD) and Transimpedance Amplifier (TIA) [6], associated with a 6 taps analog Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter which compensates the bandwidth limitations. An Error Detector (ED) compares the transmitted and received sequences to estimate the Bit Error Ratio (BER) and the transmission channel performances in real-time.

Real-time Transmission Performances

The TOSA output modulated power in the operating conditions (see Fig.2) is measured at 13.3 dBm, which represents a record performance. Fig. 5 shows the optical eye diagrams in Back-to-Back (BtB) and after 20 km propagation. An Extinction Ratio of 7.0 dB is measured in BtB and goes down to 5.8 dB after

20 km. As a result, the BtB OMA is 13.9 dBm at TOSA output.

Fig. 5: Optical eye diagram in BtB (a) and after 20 km (b).

The Transmitter and Dispersion Eye Closure (TDEC) is 1.23 dB in BtB, 1.49 dB after 20 km of fiber (44 ps/nm at 1341 nm) and 1.76 dB after 50 km of fiber (101 ps/nm at 1341 nm).

Finally, the BER measurements are presented on Fig. 6. A sensitivity of -25.2 dBm is achieved ($BER=10^{-2}$ in [2]). The measured sensitivity is consistent with our previous results with the same receiver [6] and beyond the specifications [2]. As a result, an optical budget of 38.5 dB is achieved, exceeding class D OPL requirements (20-35 dB). Fig. 6 also shows that the 15 dB dynamic range of the OPL are met.

Fig. 6: BER experimental results in back-to-back.

Discussion: High Power and Non-linearities

While the recent updates on eye safety does not suggest any risk in O-band below +22.2 dBm [14], increasing the mean launch power (MLP) affects the communications in triggering non-linear effects in the optical fiber. Stimulated Brillouin scattering seems to have a limited impact in operational conditions [15]. However, energy transfer induced by Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS) between two signals occurs when 1) signals propagating in the fiber show high powers and 2) when their optical frequency difference is close to the maximum of Raman spectral efficiency (13.2 THz). This is the case of upstream XGS-PON (1270 nm) and downstream 50G-PON (1342 nm) as the frequency difference is 12.9 THz. In [16] we reported up to 0.68 dB power depletion induced on upstream XGS-PON by downstream 50G-PON through SRS, for a downstream input power of +14 dBm (maximum of class C+), see Fig. 7. With class D, as the mean launch optical power will be higher, the risk of SRS interactions will also increase. We exploited the model developed in [17] and the

experimental results of [16] to estimate the XGS-PON depletion due to SRS beyond +14 dBm 50G-PON downstream power, see Fig. 7. As the maximum MLP step from B+ to C+ class is 4 dB, one can expect the maximum MLP of class D to be 4 dB more, then +18 dBm. As class D assumes 3 dB more OPLs than C+, a more reasonable maximum MLP power would be 3 dB higher than class C+ specification, if similar receivers are used, then +17 dBm. Up to 1.4 dB and 1.75 dB depletion are expected because of SRS on the upstream XGS-PON for a downstream 50G-PON launched power of 17 dBm and 18 dBm respectively, in case the signals propagate over 20 km of fiber. This may induce many outages for XGS-PON customers when the time for the 50G-PON deployment comes. The polarization state of both signals showed a negligible impact because of contra-propagation and natural fiber anisotropy.

Fig. 7: Upstream XGS-PON depletion induced by high power downstream 50G-PON through stimulated Raman Scattering.

Conclusions

We demonstrated record performances of a TOSA-packaged DFB-EAM-SOA emitter reaching record 13.3 dBm mean launch power in operation, 15.9 dBm in static emission and achieving 38.5 dB OPL in real-time, using a 25G-class APD receiver and a 6-taps analog FIR. The chirp is about 0.3 in the operation range, and the TOSA's bandwidth exceeds 31 GHz. This works paves the way to meet optical path loss of 35 dB and beyond, mandatory to enable massive 50G-PON deployment using class D (20-35 dB) optics. The non-linear interactions due to stimulated Raman scattering for class D transmitters are also estimated with penalties on XGS-PON transmission reaching up to 1.75 dB.

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